

**INTRODUCTION INTO ANATOMICAL HISTOLOGICAL TERMINOLOGY.
NOUN, GRAMMAR CATEGORIES OF NOUNS. DETERMINATIONS OF
GENDER, STEM, VOCABULARY FORMS**

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Abstract: This is the abstract of the histological anatomical terminologies and grammar categories of nouns. In this article there is a brief information about aforementioned topic. I have also included information about how to determine gender, stem, and vocabulary forms of the anatomical histological words.

Аннотация: Это конспект гистологической анатомической терминологии и грамматических категорий существительных. В этой статье есть краткая информация по вышеупомянутой теме. Я также включил информацию о том, как определить пол, основу и словарные формы анатомических гистологических слов.

Introduction: Anatomical terminology is a form of technique used by botanist, zoologists and health professionals. This also includes doctors and pharmacists. Most of these words are derived from latin and greek which is the stem of all these anatomical words. And these words are mainly used by doctors and health industries so the chance of misinterpretation and change is very unlikely to happen.

To illustrate how the modern day terminologies are inaccurate from the anatomical terms. Like for example how a scar above the wrist could be precisely located using anatomical terms, while doing so we eliminate errors and misinterpretation

Main Body. Nouns and grammar categories

In anatomical histological terminology. Nouns represent objects, structures just like in English. Understanding the grammar categories and nouns and critically essential for the accurate communication and interpretation in the medical field.

Determination of gender: Gender in this category doesn't follow the traditional male/gender rules like other languages, instead it relates to the grammatical gender where nouns are assigned to different categories (masculine, feminine or gender neuter) based on arbitrary rules.

Stem formation: noun stem in this often undergo modification to undergo modifications and various changes for forms, including singular and plural. These also involve suffixes, prefixes or alteration within the stem itself. These help in the precise communication in the medical field and facilitate effective among professionals in the field

Vocabulary forms: These exhibit different form to convey specific meaning. Some nouns and multiple body that vary depending on their function or context. For example: a noun might have a basic form used for general references while other forms indicate specific or dimensions of the structure being described.

Conclusion: These anatomical histological terminology relies on nouns as their primary building blocks for communication and effective interpretation and accurate description of anatomical structures. Learning all these is very crucial and essential for the professionals in the field as it reduces miscommunication and misinterpretation in the medical field.

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